

OPENLAB
ESEV

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[Educating in Freedom]

Arts, Free Software and Free Culture in Higher Education

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FCT
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[Context and origins]

- ESEV is a public institution of higher education
- founded in 1983 as a teacher education institution
- over 1500 students and 105 teachers, 9 undergraduate and 13 Master's programs (Teacher Ed., Plastic Arts and Multimedia, Media Studies, Cultural Animation, Social Education, Sports and Physical Activity and Environmental Ed.)

Minimum wage = 475€
MS Office 2013 (Student) = 120€

[Context and origins]

OpenLab emerged in 12/2009 because of the **lack of knowledge of the existing Libre alternatives** and **work habits exclusively built around proprietary software.**

(Gonçalves & Figueiredo, 2008).

Teach Ed

1 in 4 Unlicensed OS

Kompozer (32%) - 30% Unlic + DK

OO Writer (11%) - 50% Unlic + DK

Firefox (11%) - 45% Unlic + DK

Arts

1 in 3 Unlicensed OS

Firefox (40%) - 15% Unlic + DK

Software is schoolwork related

Very little F/LOSS awareness

What if? Ethical Problems!

[Context and origins]

3 > 4 teachers (voluntary basis)
4 > 5 PCs in a small room

Dissemination
Training
Support
Production

[Free as in Libre]

Not Freeware or Open Source

Freedom to run, copy, distribute, study, change and improve the software (FSF, 2012).

F0 to run the program for any purpose.

F1 to study how the program works and change it to make it do what you wish.

F2 to redistribute copies.

F3 to distribute copies of your modified versions to others.

[Software as IP]

Software tends to abundance:
Non-rivalrous consumption — — —
No additional costs for additional users

↓
Exclusion and control
mechanisms are imposed

↓
To artificially
create scarcity

↓
Protect material
rights of the owners — — — —

Commodification of
software

Creates incentives
to development

[Proprietary Software]

Programmers are driven by
self-interest

Work is organized around external incentives
Towards the accumulation of wealth

Software development
model based on competition

[Proprietary World]

“[global] companies command as much if not more power than many governments, not only to create value but also to transmit values” (Friedman, 2007, p. 508)

- Desktop users: 98% = 7% (OS X) + 91% (Windows) [1]
- in 2010, more than 2/3 of the world population was not using the Internet [2]
- Movies have budgets higher than some countries GDP and even higher box office revenue [3]
- richest 1% owns 35.4% of wealth (USA, 2010) [4]
- 6 corporations control 90% of the media (USA) [5]
- In 2012, "Apple Microsoft" is the 43rd richest country (USD 234 Billion). Above Pakistan, Portugal, Ireland, etc. UNICEF budget 2010 = 4B. [6]

[Free as in Libre]

Free Software and **Free Culture** are the natural result of an ethical choice towards a society and culture based on the free exchange of ideas and creativity, on freedom and sharing. They stand for an ecosystem that refuses the domination of the artificial barriers that benefit only a few.

[Free as in Libre]

“Free software (...) brings with it powerful new production methods and vibrant communities, which challenge artists to change the ways things of all kinds are made” (Griffiths, 2008, p. 248)

“the workflow in f/loss is not pre-determined for the artist (...) and opens a world of possibilities and creativity” (Kenlon, 2011, p. 42), refusal of the “don't do it, or spend more money to be able to do it.” (p. 41).

“It just works”

Who owns the software? Whom does it serve?

[Dissemination]

Presentations

Events

Website + Web 2.0

Room

[Training]

in-house

- > Central tenet of our activities.
- > Over 55 workshops (3-6h)
- > Diverse focus (more arts), contexts and softwares.

outside

[Training]

[Training]

Skills transfer: between students, between different programs, between different school levels

Building know-how: new skills at different school levels, not only F/LOSS related

New attitudes: continuous learning, software agnostic, collaboration, discovery and autonomous learning, internet and virtual communities

[Support]

EVTUX

Software installation

Edubuntu at Early Childhood

USB pens

[Support]

Since 2008/2009, 36% (39) of all final projects of the Arts and Multimedia graduate program (108) are developed with F/LOSS.

[Support]

14.8% (16) are short animation movies.
- Renderfarm and Libre animation

[Production]

Documentation

Curated lists

Action-coding

StudiozCollabPress
Ottographer
WebMizer
ProDISC
Festivalz
Taskz
Storyboardz

Research

Education

Arts

Infrastructure

OPERATING SYSTEM

- [Debian](#)
- [Fedora](#)
- [Linux Mint](#)
- [Ubuntu](#)
- [Ubuntu Studio](#)

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

- [GanttProject](#)
- [Plan](#)
- [Planner](#)
- [TaskJuggler](#)

BUDGET AND FINANCES

- [Buddi](#)
- [GnuCash](#)
- [Grisbi](#)
- [KMyMoney](#)

PRODUCTION/ASSET MANAGEMENT

- [Blender-ld](#)
- [Gimp](#)
- [Hugin](#)
- [MediaGoblin](#)
- [OpenPipeline](#)
- [Stalker](#)
- [oyProjectManager](#)
- [SparkleShare](#)
- [StudiosCollabPress](#)
- [Subversion](#)
- [TACTIC](#)

IMAGE MANAGEMENT

- [digiKam](#)
- [F-Spot](#)
- [Gallery](#)
- [Geeqie](#)
- [Gwenview](#)
- [KPhotoAlbum](#)
- [KSquirrel](#)
- [MediaGoblin](#)
- [Piwigo](#)
- [Shotwell](#)

FILE FORMATS

- [Alembic](#)
- [COLLADA](#)

Pre-production

IDEA & CONCEPT

- [Dia](#)
- [Flow](#)
- [FreeMind](#)
- [LibreOffice](#)
- [OpenOffice](#)
- [Visual Understanding Environment](#)

SCRIPT

- [Celtx](#)
- [LibOScreenplay](#)
- [Screenwright\(R\)](#)
- [Storybook](#)
- [Trelby](#)

STORYBOARD

- [Animix](#)
- [Celtx](#)

- [GIMP](#)
- [Krita](#)

CONCEPT ART

- [Karbon](#)
- [Agave](#)

- [GIMP Paint Studio](#)

- [gpick](#)
- [MyPaint](#)
- [Krita](#)

Production

3D MODELING

- [Arbaro](#)
- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Ayam](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [CanTree](#)
- [Insight3D](#)
- [K-3D](#)
- [Lithosphere](#)
- [MakeHuman](#)
- [MakerScanner](#)
- [MeshLab](#)
- [Misfit Model 3D](#)
- [OpenFX](#)
- [Picogen](#)
- [Seamless3d](#)

- [TopMod](#)
- [Wings 3D](#)

TEXTURING

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)

- [OpenFX](#)

LAYOUT

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [OpenFX](#)

ANIMATION

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [BVHplay](#)
- [Helix](#)
- [JLipSync](#)
- [OpenFX](#)
- [Papagayo](#)
- [QAvimator](#)

SHADING

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [OpenFX](#)
- [Open Shading Language](#)

TEXTURES

- [Blender](#)

Post-production

PAINT FIX / RETOUCH

- [CinePaint](#)
- [DJV Imaging](#)
- [Duke](#)
- [GIMP](#)
- [Hugin](#)
- [ImageMagick](#)
- [Krita](#)

VIDEO EDITING

- [Blender](#)
- [Cinelerra](#)
- [EKD](#)
- [FFmpeg](#)
- [Kdenlive](#)
- [Kino](#)
- [LiVES](#)
- [Lumiera](#)

- [Open Movie Editor](#)

- [OpenShot](#)
- [Pinnacle](#)
- [Shotcut](#)
- [slowmoVideo](#)

AUDIO EDITING

- [Ardour](#)
- [Audacity](#)
- [FluidSynth](#)
- [Hydrogen](#)
- [Jokosher](#)
- [LMMS](#)
- [MusE](#)
- [Open Octave](#)
- [Qtractor](#)
- [Rosegarden](#)
- [ReZound](#)
- [Traverso DAW](#)
- [ZynAddSubFX](#)

Distribution

CINEMA

- [Open Cinema Tools](#)
- [OpenDCP](#)

DVD

- [2ManDVD](#)
- [Bombono](#)
- [DeVeDe](#)
- [DVDAuthor](#)
- [DVD Styler](#)
- ['Q' DVD-Author](#)
- [Tovid](#)

WEB

- [Drupal](#)
- [WordPress](#)

OTHER USEFUL

- [ColorTape](#)
- [dan-abri](#)
- [FontForge](#)
- [Gnome Subtitles](#)
- [LightZone](#)
- [RawTherapee](#)
- [Scribus](#)

librepipeline.animaxionstudios.com

[SWOT]

Strengths

- Mutual Support (7)
- Training (6)
- Ethics (5)
- On-site support (5)
- Know-how (4)
- Innovation, novelty (4)
- Learning reciprocity (4)
- Team functioning (3)
- No costs (3)
- Open to community (2)

- Low visibility (6)
- Resources (5) [Space (4)]
- Team functioning (4)
- ESEV confined (3)
- Irregular activity (2)

Weaknesses

35 people identified (23) | Online and anonymously

Opportunities

- Growing interest (4) [Crisis (2)]
- Partnerships (5)
- Software Quality (3)
- Public beyond school (3)
- Schools (3)
- Businesses (3)

- Indifference (5)
- Lack of available resources (4)
- Ignorance (3)
- Prejudice (2)
- Marketing (2)

Threats

[Tomorrow? Today!]

Policy making
More colleagues & courses
Software pipelines

Physical space
New hardware
Web server (Q&A,
renderfarm, plagiarism,
Zotero, mediagoblin, etc.)

(former) Student > student
Bring experts
Smaller, more often
More Education

Python & OSL coding
3D animation movie
Documentation
More research

Partnerships

Public beyond school

Free Software is a matter of liberty, not price. Using Free Software is a statement about the world we live in and how we choose to live in it.

openlab.esev.ipv.pt
nafergo.intervir.net

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IMAGES

Screen 2: adapted from Google Maps

Screen 4: adapted from "organize!" by worker
(<http://openclipart.org/detail/102679/organize!-by-worker>)

Screen 5: "Heckert GNU white" by Anomie
(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Heckert_GNU_white.svg) & "Tux" by Tene
(<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Tux.png>)

Screen 8: composition based on "crashing wave" by johnny automatic
(http://openclipart.org/detail/3166/crashing-wave-by-johnny_automatic), "comic characters:
flag" by nicubuntu (<http://openclipart.org/detail/21872/comic-characters:-flag-by-nicubunu>),
"free software gang" (<http://www.fsf.org/working-together/gang>) and organization logos

Screen 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17: OpenLab ESEV image archive

Screen 21: nafergo

NOTES

[1] Desktop, laptop, netbook (Web Analytics) (<http://www.netmarketshare.com>)

[2] International Telecommunications Union.

<http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Documents/facts/ICTFactsFigures2013.pdf>

[3] World Bank (<http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>) and
Box Office Mojo (<http://www.boxofficemojo.com/movies/?id=ironman3.htm>)

[4] Domhoff , G. W. (2003). Power in America: Wealth, Income, and Power. Retrieved from
<http://sociology.ucsc.edu/whorulesamerica/power/wealth.html>

[5]

<http://www.globalissues.org/article/159/media-conglomerates-mergers-concentration-of-ownership>

[6] http://www.unicef.org/about/.../UNICEF_finance_and_budget_17Jan2012.pdf